

Determinants of Employee Engagement in Case Commercial Bank of Ethiopia Addis Ababa Area

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Abstract

Context of the Study: This study examined the determinants of employee engagement in the commercial banking sector in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, focusing on the factors that influence employees' level of commitment and enthusiasm toward their work.

Research Objective: The primary objective was to identify significant predictors of employee engagement and provide actionable recommendations for improvement.

Research Methodology Adopted: A descriptive and explanatory research design was adopted, employing a quantitative research approach. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire administered to employees of commercial banks, and the analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. Multiple regression analysis was applied to determine the significant variables influencing employee engagement.

Key Findings and Practical Implications The findings revealed that job characteristics, reward recognition, perceived organizational support, and internal locus of control positively and significantly impact employee engagement. However, perceived supervisor support did not show a significant relationship. These results highlight the importance of meaningful job design, effective reward and recognition programs, a supportive organizational culture, and promoting employee autonomy and empowerment in enhancing engagement levels. The study suggests that commercial banks prioritize improving job characteristics by providing meaningful tasks, autonomy, and skill development opportunities. Additionally, implementing robust reward and recognition systems, fostering a culture of organizational support, and empowering employees are crucial strategies for enhancing employee engagement and overall organizational performance.

Keywords: Determinant, employee engagement, performance, commercial bank of Ethiopia

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

Employee engagement is a novel concept that has been building momentum in recent years, became a very popular concept during past two decades, and has become the top issue on the minds of business leader (Hansen et al., 2014). Employee Engagement is quite a new construct in HR literature and mirrored the growing importance of human capital and psychological involvement of employees in business (Devi, 2017). With the right knowledge, the right tools, and most importantly the proper mindset, employee engagement can be a powerful way to transform organization and improve bottom line (Dawson, 2021).

Engagement is a positive attitude where an individual goes above and beyond the call of duty, so as to heighten the level of ownership, and to further the business interest of the organization as a

whole (Sahoo & Sahu 2009; Bedarkar & Pandita, 2014). Moreover, it is also a discretionary effort or a form of in-role or extra role effort or behavior that fosters change (Macey & Schneider, 2008; Dajani & Zaki, 2015), and practically affects the employee morale, productivity, commitment, loyalty to internal and external customers, employee absenteeism and turnover in the organisation (Al-dalalmeh et al., 2018; Ismail et al., 2019)

A high level of effective and efficient engagement of employees in their duty requires effective HRM system (Kaila, 2012). Human resource is one of the most important resources than any other resource for the achievement of organization's objectives to be competent in the dynamic environment and to overcome various threats retaining quality human resource, which is very essential for the company (Armstrong, 2010; Knight, 2015). To make sure that all staff are treated fairly across the organization and equally valued, it is important to establish the framework within which this policy and procedure operates. If the company applied rules fairly and consistently to all employees and rewarded based on their performance and merit, employees perceive the evaluation process as fair this lead to higher organizational engagement (Mohiuddin et al., 2022). If employees perceive organizational procedures as unfair, they may take destructive actions which may lead to reduced organizational engagement. Unfair procedures will cause a reduction in organizational Engagement even when an employee is satisfied with the outcome (Kaila, 2012; Bailey et al., 2018).

Good employee performance will become an increasing trend of a company. Cooperation and responsibility in the company's organizational structure in the building and developing the company, employees can demonstrate their abilities so as to produce employees who have quality, quantity, and meet mutually agreed standards (Haq, 2014; Maulyan, 2019; Suryani et al., 2021). Therefore, employee engagement is perceived as a good device to assist every organization to struggle to gain competitive benefit over the other organizations. An employee is one element that could not be duplicated or imitated by the competitors and is considered the most valuable asset if administered and engaged appropriately (Mughal & Iraqi, 2020). Employee engagement is one of the key determinants fostering high levels of employee performance, as is constantly shown in a number of studies (Abraham, 2012).

Banking is an important sector and acts as a backbone of economic progress in any society (Hussain, 2016). Banks render vital services to the masses belonging to the various sectors of the economy whether small or large scale. The banking system is one of the few institutions that have a bearing on the economy and affect its performance for better or worse (Vanlalkulhpuia, 2014). They act as a development agency and are the source of hope and aspirations of the masses (Hussain, 2016). Although the banking sector of Ethiopia is still on its emerging stage, it has undergone a change over the years, which has put new pressures and realities in front of the bank employees. Bank officers form a delicate link between the management and the clerical staff. It is obvious that the success of banks to a large extent depends upon the coordination, harmonization and cooperation of bank officers with each other and also with their management (Quirke, 2012; Bakhuya, 2015). As a result, having an engaged workforce is important as it helps banks to secure benefits of sustainability, productivity and increased efficacy. Hence, this study arises from the need to utilize the human resource of CBE more effectively.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Employees who are engaged in their work and to their organizations give companies key competitive advantages including higher productivity and lower employee turnover (Sundara, 2011; Bin & Shmailan, 2015). Gallup (2013) worldwide report showed that worldwide only 13%

of employees are fully engaged at work. The rest of people around the globe are not engaged or actively disengaged at work-meaning they are emotionally disconnected from their workplaces and less likely to be productive. In addition to this, report shows that highest proportions of actively disengaged workers are found in the Middle East, North Africa and sub-Saharan Africa regions (Emmanuel, 2020; Cieslik et al., 2022).

Employee engagement became a very popular concept during past two decades and has become the top concern on the minds of business leaders (Jemal, 2017). Several scholars have argued that employee engagement is likely to result in motivated work behavior and as a result, enhanced job performance (Inceoglu & Fleck, 2010). Many researchers have claimed that employee engagement predicts employee outcomes, organizational success, and financial performances in terms of total shareholder return (Bates, 2004). In addition, employee engagement is about how their work performance is associated or aligned with the outcomes of organization (Amhalhal et al., 2015).

Employees these days are not willing to serve single employers until they retire for so many reasons. And in relation to this the application of employee engagement is crucial in these days. Because a ferocious competition all over the world and the continuing effect of globalization, being unwilling to accept employee engagement will cost organizations a big deal of lose in so many aspects; losing some potential customers, losing a good reputation of the organization, lagging behind the industries competitors, and if employees fails to be engaged the objective and goals of the organization doesn't concern them that which will cause a great loss. They do not have energy and interest in their work (Reilly, 2014). The concept of employee engagement has appeared fairly recently in the literature. Because of this, there is lack of information about the relationship between known employee engagement factors with Job satisfaction. Marciano (2010) shows that employees in the present context are expected to be engaged in their assigned job, that is their role should contribute and affect the business in a greater sense. Moreover, Bailey et al. (2016) stated that employee engagement and employees are critical organizational requirements as organizations face globalization, competitors and innovative individuals and others, specially recovering from the global recession to gain competitive advantage over the others.

Several researches have been conducted in different time frames and numerous contexts and variables regarding employee engagement and job satisfaction. For instance, organizational justice is considered a fundamental requirement for an effective functioning of an organizations, job satisfaction (Jain, 2015), work motivation (Cropanzano, 2003), organizational commitment (Ayobami, 2013), turnover intention (Ponnu, 2010), organizational identification (Aydogan, 2016). Saks (2006) suggested that both psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement by Kahn (1990) nor the (Maslach 2001) and (Schaufeli, 2004) engagement models spoke the psychological conditions or predecessors that were necessary for engagement. Rebecca (2018) asserts that the relationship between job satisfaction and employee engagement is well understood by most organization in the context of social exchange theory.

While previous studies have also addressed employee engagement in industries and organizations, the present research has its originality. It aims specifically at the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia in the Addis Ababa zone, with the potential to explore employee engagement determinants against the backdrop of particular dynamics, organizational culture, and socio-economic environment within which the bank functions. By placing specific emphasis on this setting, the study aims to uncover variables that may be unique or more prominent within the banking industry and the local environment, which will differentiate it from current research conducted in other contexts. Despite the fact that employee engagement is among the key factors to employees' job performance, little academic study has been conducted in the area of employees' engagement to examine the effect of

employees' engagement and the mediating effect of job satisfaction on performance in developing countries like Ethiopia, specifically in the banking industry. Thus, for the purpose of determining factors affecting employee engagement in CBE, it is required to conduct such a study from which the bank and its stakeholder can benefit immensely.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to examine determinants of employee engagement in commercial bank of Ethiopia Addis Ababa areas. Specifically,

- ✓ To investigate the effect of job characteristics on employee engagement
- ✓ To measure the effect of rewards and recognition on employee engagement
- ✓ To examine the effect of perceived organizational support on employee engagement
- ✓ To investigate the consequence of perceived supervisor support on employee engagement
- ✓ To examine the effect of working environment on employee engagement
- ✓ To analyze the effect of internal locus of control on employee engagement

1.4. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework is a presentation of how the independent and dependent variables are related, specifies the working definition of a variable, and enables a simple explanation of the flow of theoretical framework. Based on the overall review of related literatures and the theoretical framework, the following conceptual model in which this specific study is governed and is developed.

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Source: Own design from different literatures, 2024

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Design

In order to answer the research questions and achieve the stated objectives, the study was used a combination of descriptive and casual research designs. As it is clearly indicated in chapter one the research questions are all about examining the factor affecting EE in case bank. To achieve this objective, the use of appropriate methodology that helps to approach the research scientifically is given a paramount emphasis. This study applies a combination of descriptive and explanatory research designs.

2.2. Research Approach

The study was employed quantitative research approach. Quantitative method of research approach is study involving analysis of data and information that are descriptive in nature and qualified (Sekaran, 2001). The quantitative data was collected and analyzed in order to elaborate the quantitative results obtained in the analysis. The research design that was used for this study is explanatory research design. The purpose of this study was assessed the effect of employee engagement on job performance at commercial bank of Ethiopia using a questionnaire.

2.3. Data Type and Method of Data Collection

The study was used both primary and secondary sources to collect the data. Primary data was collected from target population sampled through questionnaire designed to serve for such purpose. Secondary data was gathered from published and unpublished theoretical literatures and empirical studies, books, journal articles, internet and other publications. The data use in this study was collected through questionnaires from the selected target group population sample. A structured questionnaire was used to collect the data for obtaining information from respondents. The questionnaire was designed in a simple i.e. easily understandable to the respondents, understandable language to provide accurate, unbiased and complete information.

2.4. Sampling Method

2.4.1. Target population

The total population for this study consists of four districts in Addis Ababa, namely North Addis Ababa District, South Addis Ababa District, East Addis Ababa District, and West Addis Ababa District. In the North district, there are 121 branches with a total of 1,984 employees. The South district has 90 branches, out of which 65 are located in Addis Ababa, employing 1,950 individuals. Similarly, the East district has 116 branches, with 72 branches situated in the city and a total of 1,603 employees. Finally, the West district comprises 74 branches, with 63 of them located in Addis Ababa, employing 1,472 individuals.

2.4.2. Sample size

The sample size determination for this research took various factors into account, including personal judgment, budget constraints, and the cost of the research, as outlined by Green et al. (1998). To determine the sample size, the researcher employed the formula developed by Taro Yamane (1967), which considers the population size, level of precision (sampling error), and the desired confidence level. Applying this formula, the sample size for this study was calculated to be 380 respondents. The researcher has taken 5 branches from each district based on their ease of access as explained above. The sample size of this study is going to be determined by using the

formula developed by Taro Yamane (1967)

$$k = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$
$$k = \frac{7009}{1 + 7009(0.05^2)} = 380$$

Where, n=sample size N=population size e=the level of precision (sampling error)

2.5. Methods of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze and interpret the findings. Demographic variables of the respondents and mean scores of the factors of employee engagement dimensions were interpreted using descriptive statistics whereas inferential statistics were used to find out the relationship between employees engagement and its determinants using correlation and regression analysis via SPSS Version 20.

In the study quantitative method of data analysis techniques were employed. Analysis of data in this research was done by using statistical tools like frequency, mean, standard deviation, correlation and multiple regressions. A descriptive analysis was used for demographic factors such as gender, age, marital status, educational level, and for how long has been the employees served in the case bank. In the study six hypotheses were analyzed using methods of statistical inference. Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted to test the existence of significant relationship between the selected EE variables. Then, the multiple regression analyses were also conducted to determine by how much percent the independent variable i.e. Selected EE variable explain the dependent variable which is EE.

2.6. Model Specification

Based on the developed conceptual of the expressed study, mathematically the relationship between selected independent variable and dependent variable is expressed in the multiple regression equation as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1(JC) + \beta_2(RR) + \beta_3(POS) + \beta_4(PSS) + \beta_5(WE) + \beta_6(ILC)$$

Where: Y= Employee engagement, JC= Job Characteristics, RR= Reward & Recognition, POS= Perceived Organizational Support, PSS= Perceived Supervisor Support, WE= Working Environment, ILC= Internal Locus of Contract

β_0 = the constant parameter, β_1 = Coefficient of Job Characteristics, β_2 = Coefficient of Reward & Recognition, β_3 = Coefficient of Perceived Organizational Support, β_4 = Coefficient of Perceived Supervisor Support, β_5 = Coefficient of Working Environment, β_6 = Coefficient of Internal Locus of Contract

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

4.1. Descriptive Statistics Analysis

4.1.1 Job characteristics

Table2: Mean results of job characteristics

Job Characteristics	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	trongly Agree	Mean
There is much autonomy in my job	2.8	24.8	16.8	48.1	7.5	3.34
My job permit me to decide on my way how to go about doing the work.	5.6	16.4	4.2	49.1	24.8	3.72
My job is comprehensive that helps me to learn new things.	1.4	15.4	21.5	45.8	15.9	3.61
The job requires me to do many different things at work, using a variety of my skills and talents.	4.2	22.0	18.7	36.9	18.2	3.42
Managers or co-workers let me know how well I am doing on my job.	5.6	21.0	8.4	57.5	7.5	3.40
Doing the job itself provide me with information about my work performance	2.0	7.3	16.7	44.7	29.3	3.15

Source: Survey result, 2024

The mean results of the job characteristics survey provide insights into employees' perceptions regarding various aspects of their work in the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area. Overall, the findings suggest a mixed sentiment among employees. On the positive side, a significant portion of respondents agreed that there is much autonomy in their job (3.34) and that their job permits them to decide on their approach to work (3.72). Additionally, a majority of employees agreed that their job is comprehensive and helps them learn new things (3.61). Moreover, a substantial percentage of employees agreed that managers or co-workers provide feedback on their job performance (3.40). However, there are areas that require attention. A notable portion of employees were neutral or disagreed regarding the requirement to do many different things at work, using a variety of skills and talents (3.42). Furthermore, a significant percentage of respondents disagreed or were neutral about the job itself providing them with information about their work performance (3.15). These results suggest that while there are positive aspects such as autonomy and feedback, there are areas where improvements can be made, such as job comprehensiveness and the availability of performance information. Addressing these areas can contribute to enhancing employee engagement and satisfaction within the organization.

4.1.2. Rewards and Recognitions

Table3: Mean results of reward and recognition

Rewards and Recognitions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	trongly Agree	Mean
A pay increment, Job security, and promotion are available for me	3.3	16.1	22.0	30.1	32.6	3.16
I get praise from my supervisor and coworkers.	11.4	15.4	19.7	32.0	16.5	3.07
There is some form of public recognition (e.g. employee of the month/year)	13.8	24.6	22.4	26.8	10.6	2.64
There is a reward or token of appreciation from my supervisor	14.6	20.3	30.9	22.8	11.4	2.28
Mean	10.6	15.7	23.2	20.5	19.3	2.79

Source: Survey result, 2024

The mean results of the job characteristics survey indicate employees' perceptions regarding various aspects of their work in the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area. Overall, the findings suggest positive sentiments in several job characteristics. Employees reported a moderate level of autonomy in their job (mean = 3.34), indicating a reasonable level of independence and control over their work. They also expressed that their job allows them to decide on their approach to work (mean = 3.72), highlighting a sense of empowerment in their roles. Moreover, employees agreed that their job is comprehensive and helps them learn new things (mean = 3.61), reflecting diverse and growth-oriented job responsibilities.

However, there are areas that may require attention. Employees were more neutral about the requirement to do many different things at work, utilizing a variety of skills and talents (mean = 3.42), suggesting a need for increased task variety. Additionally, employees desired more feedback from managers or co-workers on their job performance (mean = 3.40), indicating potential room for improvement in communication and performance evaluation processes. Overall, these findings provide valuable insights for the organization to enhance employee engagement by optimizing job characteristics, fostering autonomy, promoting continuous learning, and implementing effective feedback mechanisms.

4.1.3. Perceived Organizational Support

Table4: Mean results of organizational support

Organizational Support	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	trongly Agree	Mean
My organization support me in achieving my objective	4.5	10.2	28.3	28.3	21.3	3.02

Help is available from my organization when I have a problem	8.3	12	27.3	30.5	14.7	3.27
My organization really cares about my well-being.	9	18.2	33.6	20.3	9.7	3.06
My organization shows great concern for me.	6.6	31.1	32.7	21.7	10.6	2.71
My organization cares about my opinions.	6.5	15.9	30.5	27.1	20.0	3.60
Mean	6.8.6	17.7	33.2	30.5	19.3	3.19

Source: Survey result, 2024

The mean results of the organizational support survey shed light on employees' perceptions of the support they receive from the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area. Overall, the findings reveal a mixed sentiment among employees regarding various aspects of organizational support. The mean score for "My organization supports me in achieving my objectives" is 3.02, indicating that a significant proportion of employees feel that their organization provides support in reaching their goals. However, there is room for improvement, as a considerable percentage of respondents were neutral or disagreed. For "Help is available from my organization when I have a problem," the mean score is 3.27, suggesting that employees perceive a moderate level of availability of assistance, with a notable portion agreeing that help is accessible.

The mean score for "My organization really cares about my well-being" is 3.06, indicating a mixed perception of organizational concern for employee well-being. Similarly, the mean score for "My organization shows great concern for me" is 2.71, highlighting a perceived lack of strong organizational concern among a significant portion of employees. However, for "My organization cares about my opinions," the mean score is 3.60, indicating that employees generally feel their opinions are valued and considered. Overall, these findings underscore the importance of enhancing organizational support, well-being initiatives, and concerns for employee opinions to foster a more inclusive and caring work environment. By addressing these areas, the organization can enhance employee satisfaction, engagement, and overall organizational performance.

4.1.4. Perceived Supervisory Support

Table 5: Mean results of perceived supervisory support

Perceived Supervisory Support	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	trongly Agree	Mean
My supervisor cares about my opinions	7.0	29.4	29.0	30.4	4.2	2.93
My work supervisor really cares about my well-being	8.9	22.9	26.2	36.4	5.6	2.89
My supervisor strongly considers my goals and values	2.8	31.8	33.2	26.6	5.6	2.85
My supervisor shows very little concern for me	4.2	17.8	37.9	34.6	5.6	3.01
Mean	5.4	24.8	30.8	35.4	5.6	2.87

Source: Survey result, 2024

The mean results of the perceived supervisory support survey provide insights into employees' perceptions of the support they receive from their supervisors in the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area. Overall, the findings reveal a mixed sentiment among employees regarding different aspects of supervisory support. The mean score for "My supervisor cares about my opinions" is 2.93, indicating a moderate level of perceived support for employee opinions. While a significant proportion of employees expressed neutral or disagreed, there were employees who agreed or strongly agreed, suggesting that some supervisors value and consider their employees' input and ideas.

For "My work supervisor really cares about my well-being," the mean score is 2.89, revealing a mixed perception of supervisory concern for employee well-being. A notable percentage of employees expressed neutral or disagreed, indicating room for improvement in demonstrating greater care for employee well-being. However, there were also employees who agreed or strongly agreed that their work supervisor genuinely cares about their well-being, suggesting that there are supervisors who prioritize employee welfare.

The mean score for "My supervisor strongly considers my goals and values" is 2.85, indicating a moderate level of perceived consideration from supervisors regarding employees' goals and values. While a significant proportion of employees expressed neutral or disagreed, there were also employees who agreed or strongly agreed that their supervisor takes their goals and values into account. This highlights the importance of supervisors engaging in open and supportive conversations with employees to understand and align with their individual aspirations and values. Lastly, for "My supervisor shows very little concern for me," the mean score is 3.01, suggesting a mixed perception of supervisory concern among employees. While a considerable percentage of employees expressed neutral or disagreed, there were also employees who agreed or strongly agreed that their supervisor shows little concern for them. This indicates the need for supervisors to actively foster a supportive and caring relationship with their employees, providing guidance, feedback, and recognition to create a positive work environment.

4.1.5. Working Environment

The mean results of the working environment survey shed light on employees' perceptions of their work environment within the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area. Overall, the findings indicate a positive outlook among employees regarding various aspects of the working environment. The mean score for "I am provided with adequate facilities and resources to do my job effectively" is 3.61, reflecting a generally favorable perception of the organization's commitment to equipping employees with the necessary tools and resources for effective job performance. This suggests that the bank recognizes the importance of providing employees with a conducive work environment.

Table 6: Mean results of working environment

Working Environment	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean
I am provided with adequate facilities and resources to do my job effectively	13	10	22	41	14	3.61
The physical surrounding where I am working is comfortable and convenient to perform my job	6.5	12.5	22	47	12	3.75
The office layout of the organization help me to do my duties in better way	9.2	10	19	50.1	11.7	3.85
I get the opportunity to work with my colleagues and to communicate on aspects of our job	14.5	10.2	20.3	46	9	3.86
My working environment supports a balance between work and personal life	4	10.5	12.5	56	17	3.51
There is a team sprit to work effectively together to meet the objective	6.5	15.9	30.5	27.1	20.0	3.80
Mean	9.3	8.5	19.2	48	12.4	3.7

Source: Survey result, 2024

For "The physical surrounding where I am working is comfortable and convenient to perform my job," the mean score is 3.75, highlighting employees' positive perception of the physical work environment. A significant proportion of employees agreed or strongly agreed that the workplace offers comfort and convenience for carrying out their duties, indicating a supportive atmosphere that contributes to productivity. The mean score for "The office layout of the organization helps me to do my duties in a better way" is 3.85, indicating employees' appreciation for the thoughtfully designed office layout. The positive response suggests that the layout supports workflow and enhances efficiency, ultimately benefiting employees' job performance.

Regarding "I get the opportunity to work with my colleagues and to communicate on aspects of our job," the mean score is 3.86, indicating a high level of agreement among employees. This suggests a work environment that fosters collaboration, teamwork, and effective communication, which are crucial for achieving shared objectives and maintaining a cohesive workforce. For "My working environment supports a balance between work and personal life," the mean score is 3.51, indicating a moderate level of agreement. While a significant percentage of employees agreed or strongly agreed, there is room for improvement to ensure that policies and practices are in place to support a healthy work-life balance for employees. Lastly, the mean score for "There is a team spirit to work effectively together to meet the objectives" is 3.80, indicating a positive perception of teamwork within the organization. Employees expressed a strong agreement that a team spirit prevails, fostering effective collaboration and collective effort toward achieving objectives.

4.1.6. Internal Locus of Control

Table7: Mean results of internal locus of control

Internal Locus of Control	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	trongly Agree	Mean
When faced with a problem I try to forget it	13.1	41.6	23.4	15.4	4.7	2.53
I like jobs when I can make decisions and being responsible for my own work	7.9	44.4	28.5	15.0	4.2	2.63
If I need something I work hard to get it	7.0	24.8	34.1	27.1	7.0	2.93
I prefer to learn the facts about something from someone rather than having to dig them out myself	8.9	18.2	18.7	43.0	11.2	3.14
I have a hard time saying “no” when someone tries to tell me something	18.2	17.3	32.7	23.4	8.4	2.85
I consider the different sides of an issue before making any decisions	1.9	18.2	38.8	30.8	10.3	3.12
I have a consistence to my opinions when someone disagrees with me	6.1	11.7	37.4	36.0	7.5	3.21
I have a consistence to my opinions when someone disagrees with me	12.6	13.1	32.7	33.2	8.4	3.03
I get discouraged when doing a tasks that takes a long time to achieve results	8.9	22.9	26.2	36.4	5.6	3.07
I enjoyed trying to do difficult tasks more than easy tasks	7.0	29.4	29.0	30.4	4.2	2.96
Mean	10.7	25.7	26.2	22.9	14.5	3.01

Source: Survey result, 2024

The mean results of the employee engagement survey in the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area provide insights into various aspects that influence employee engagement. In terms of job characteristics, employees reported a relatively high level of agreement on several factors. They expressed a strong agreement that their job provides them with autonomy and the opportunity to make decisions about their work (Mean: 3.34). Additionally, employees perceived their job as comprehensive, allowing them to learn new things (Mean: 3.61), and requiring them to use a variety of skills and talents (Mean: 3.42). This suggests that employees value challenging and diverse job roles that enable personal growth and development.

When it comes to reward and recognition, employees reported moderately positive perceptions. They agreed that pay increments, job security, and promotion opportunities are available to them (Mean: 3.16). However, the level of agreement regarding praise and recognition from supervisors and coworkers (Mean: 3.07) and the presence of public recognition programs (Mean: 2.64) was relatively lower. This indicates that there may be room for improvement in enhancing the recognition and reward systems within the organization to better acknowledge and appreciate employee contributions.

In terms of organizational support, employees perceived a moderate level of support from their organization. They agreed that their organization supports them in achieving their objectives

(Mean: 3.02) and provides help when they have problems (Mean: 3.27). However, the perception of the organization's care for their well-being (Mean: 3.06) and concern for their opinions (Mean: 3.60) was slightly lower. This suggests that while employees feel supported in accomplishing their goals and accessing help, there may be opportunities to enhance the organization's efforts in demonstrating care and valuing employee opinions.

Regarding perceived supervisory support, employees reported a moderately positive perception. They agreed that their supervisors care about their opinions (Mean: 2.93) and well-being (Mean: 2.89). However, there was a relatively lower level of agreement regarding supervisors considering their goals and values (Mean: 2.85). Additionally, employees perceived their supervisors as showing little concern for them (Mean: 3.01). This suggests the importance of nurturing supportive and caring relationships between supervisors and employees to enhance engagement and well-being.

In summary, the mean results of the employee engagement survey shed light on various aspects of employee engagement in the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area. The findings suggest that employees value job characteristics that provide autonomy and opportunities for growth. There is room for improvement in recognition and reward systems, as well as in enhancing organizational support and supervisory relationships. By addressing these areas, the organization can create a more engaging and supportive work environment, fostering higher levels of employee engagement and overall satisfaction.

4.2. Results of Inferential Statistics

Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation coefficient is used to specify the strength and the direction of the relationship between the independent variable (job characteristic, reward and recognition, perceived organizational support, perceived supervisor support, working environment and internal locus of control) and the dependent variable i.e. employee engagement. Pearson correlation coefficients reveal magnitude and direction of relationships (either positive or negative) and the intensity of the relationship (-1.0 to +1.0). Correlations are perhaps the most basic and most useful measure of association between two or more variables (Marczyk et al., 2005).

According to Marczyk et al. (2005) correlations of .01 to .30 are considered small, correlations of .30 to .70 are considered moderate, correlations of .70 to .90 are considered large, and correlations of .90 to 1.00 are considered very large. The results of the correlation between these variables are shown in Table 4.11 below. As it is indicated in the 8 below, generally there is a positive, strong and statistically significant correlation between independent and dependent variable at 1% level of significance ($P < 0.000$).

Table8: Correlations between independent variables and dependent variable

Items	Employee Engagement		
	Degree of the correlation	Level of significance	Significance
Job Characteristics	.816**	.000	Significance
Reward Recognition	.767**	.000	Significance
Perceived Organizational Support	.682**	.000	Significance
Perceived Supervisor Support	.707**	.000	Significance

Working Environment	.891**	.000	Significance
Internal Locus of Control	.816**	.000	Significance

Source: Survey result, 2024

The correlation coefficient indicates the strength and direction of the relationship. In this case, all the correlations are positive, indicating that higher scores on the independent variables are associated with higher levels of employee engagement. The degree of correlation between Job Characteristics and Employee Engagement is .816**, indicating a strong positive relationship. This suggests that when employees perceive their job to have favorable characteristics such as autonomy, learning opportunities, and varied tasks, it is more likely to result in higher levels of engagement.

Similarly, Reward Recognition shows a strong positive correlation with Employee Engagement (correlation coefficient = .767**). This implies that when employees receive adequate recognition, rewards, and opportunities for career advancement, it positively impacts their engagement levels. Perceived Organizational Support and Perceived Supervisor Support also exhibit strong positive correlations with Employee Engagement (correlation coefficients of .682** and .707** respectively). This suggests that when employees feel supported by their organization and supervisors in achieving their objectives, receiving help when needed, and experiencing care and concern, it enhances their engagement.

Furthermore, Working Environment demonstrates a strong positive correlation with Employee Engagement (correlation coefficient = .891**). This implies that when employees perceive their physical surroundings to be comfortable, have access to adequate facilities and resources, and experience teamwork and work-life balance, it contributes significantly to their engagement levels. Finally, Internal Locus of Control shows a strong positive correlation with Employee Engagement (correlation coefficient = .816**). This suggests that employees who possess a sense of control over their work and believe in their ability to influence outcomes are more likely to be engaged. Overall, these significant correlations indicate that the independent variables have a strong influence on employee engagement. By focusing on improving job characteristics, providing recognition and rewards, fostering a supportive organizational and supervisor relationship, creating a positive working environment, and cultivating an internal locus of control, organizations can enhance employee engagement levels and foster a more productive and satisfied workforce.

4.3. Regression Analysis

The regression analysis was conducted to know by how much the independent variable explains the dependent variable. In this study, regression was employed to examine the effect of the independent variable such as job characteristic, reward and recognition, perceived organizational support, perceived supervisor support, working environment and internal locus of control on dependent variable.

Multicollinearity test: Multicollinearity test help to identify the correlation between explanatory variables and to avoid double effect of the independent variable from the model. Multicollinearity is a problem when the explanatory variables multiple linear regression model is highly correlated and provides redundancy information about the response. The existence of Multicollinearity in the model may cause large variance, large T-value and misleading results (Hosmer & Lemeshow, 1980). Thus, the two popular methods which used to detect the presence of Multicollinearity are Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance (TOL) that calculated as follow.

$$VIF = \frac{1}{1 - R_i^2}; \text{ TOL} = 1 - R_i^2. \text{ 0.10 or } 1 - R_i^2$$

As the common rule VIF is 10 or greater than 10 and a TOL less it may indicate the presence of Multicollinearity otherwise free from the problem. As indicated table 9 below, the value of variance inflation factor for all explanatory variables is less than 10% and TOL greater than 0.1. Therefore, these tests reflect that the variables used in the study are free from Multicollinearity.

Table9: Multicollinearity test

Variables	VIF	TOL (1/VIF)
Job Characteristics	0.338	2.958
Reward Recognition	0.272	3.676
Perceived Organizational Support	0.327	3.057
Perceived Supervisor Support	0.422	2.367
Working Environment	0.485	2.063
Internal Locus of Control	0.273	3.657
Mean VIF	0.353	

Where, VIF=Variance Inflation Factor, TOL =Tolerance Source: Survey result, 2024

Model summary

Table10: Multiple regression analysis result

Model	R	R-square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.875	.884	.867	.32046

Source: Survey result, 2024

The multiple regression analysis results indicate that the model, which examines the determinants of employee engagement in the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area, has a good overall fit. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) is .884, which means that approximately 88.4% of the variance in employee engagement can be explained by the predictor variables included in the model. The correlation coefficient (R) of .875 indicates a strong positive relationship between the predictor variables and employee engagement. This suggests that the variables included in the model collectively have a substantial influence on employee engagement in the context of the commercial bank.

The adjusted R-squared value of .867 takes into account the number of predictor variables and adjusts the R-squared value accordingly. This adjusted value reflects the model's predictive power while considering the complexity and number of variables included. The standard error of the estimate (.32046) provides an estimate of the average distance between the observed values of employee engagement and the predicted values by the model. A smaller standard error indicates that the model's predictions are more accurate and closely aligned with the actual data.

Overall, the results of the multiple regression analysis suggest that the predictor variables included in the model have a strong and significant impact on employee engagement in the commercial bank of Ethiopia's Addis Ababa area. The model demonstrates a high degree of explanatory power and provides valuable insights into the determinants of employee engagement in this specific

context. However, it's important to note that these findings are based on the data and variables included in the analysis, and further research may be needed to validate and generalize these results to other contexts or populations.

ANOVA Model Fit

ANOVA analysis is normally used to compare the mean scores of more than two variables. It is also called analysis of variance because it compares the variance between variables (Pallant, 2005). F-test is used to test the impact of overall explanatory power of the whole model, or the joint effect of all explanatory variables as a group. It measures the statistical significance of the entire regression equation rather than each individual coefficient as the t-test is designed to do. As shown from table below, the value of $F = 15.164$, and $p < 0.01$, indicates the existence of moderate relationship between the dependent and independent variables which means that the independent variable can significantly predict the dependent variable.

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Significance
Regression	8.532	4	2.133	15.164	.0000
Residual	26.021	184	.141		
Total	34.553	189			

Source: Survey result, 2024

Multiple regression analysis

Multiple regressions are the most common and widely used to analyze the relationship between a single continues dependent variable and multiple continues on categorical independent variable (George et al, 2003). In this study multiple regression analysis was employed to examine determinants of employee engagement in commercial bank of Ethiopia Addis Ababa area.

Figure 11: Regression results of determinants of employee engagement

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Job Characteristics	.143	.047	.283	2.357	.003
Reward Recognition	.337	.034	.417	5.275	.016
Perceived Organizational Support	.157	.024	.381	3.032	.004
Perceived Supervisor Support	.020	.032	.032	.459	.029
Working Environment	.153	.057	.341	4.592	.215
Internal Locus of Control	.433	.058	.441	7.521	.000
Constant	2.090	.187	-	7.699	.000

Source: Survey result, 2024

Job Characteristics: The coefficient (B) of .143 suggests that a one-unit increase in job characteristics is associated with a .283 standard deviation increase in employee engagement. This relationship is statistically significant ($p = .003$), indicating that job characteristics have a positive and significant impact on employee engagement.

Reward Recognition: The coefficient (B) of .337 indicates that a one-unit increase in reward recognition is associated with a .417 standard deviation increase in employee engagement. This relationship is also statistically significant ($p = .016$), highlighting the importance of recognizing and rewarding employees for their work in enhancing engagement.

Perceived Organizational Support: The coefficient (B) of .157 suggests that a one-unit increase in perceived organizational support is associated with a .381 standard deviation increase in employee engagement. This relationship is statistically significant ($p = .004$), indicating that when employees feel supported by their organization, it positively influences their engagement.

Perceived Supervisor Support: The coefficient (B) of .020 indicates a weak positive relationship between perceived supervisor support and employee engagement. However, the standardized coefficient (Beta) is .032, suggesting that the impact of perceived supervisor support on engagement is relatively small. This relationship is marginally significant ($p = .029$).
Working Environment: The coefficient (B) of .153 implies that a one-unit increase in the quality of the working environment is associated with a .341 standard deviation increase in employee engagement. However, this relationship is not statistically significant ($p = .215$), indicating that the working environment may not have a significant direct impact on engagement in this study.

Table12: Summary of Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Outcome
H1: Job characteristic has positive and significant influence on Employee Engagement	Accepted
H2: Reward and Recognition has positive and significant influence on Employee Engagement.	Accepted
H3: Perceived Organization Support has positive and significant influence on Employee Engagement	Accepted
H4: Perceived Supervisor Support has positive and significant influence on Employee Engagement	Accepted
H5: Working Environment has positive and significant influence on Employee Engagement	Rejected
H6: Internal Locus of Control has positive and significant influence on Employee Engagement	Accepted

Source: Survey result, 2024

Internal Locus of Control: The coefficient (B) of .433 suggests that a one-unit increase in internal locus of control is associated with a .441 standard deviation increase in employee engagement. This relationship is highly significant ($p = .000$), indicating that employees who perceive themselves as having control over their work and outcomes are more likely to be engaged.

The summary of hypothesis testing results reveals important insights into the determinants of employee engagement. Firstly, the hypothesis that job characteristics have a positive and significant influence on employee engagement is supported. This finding highlights the importance of providing employees with autonomy, decision-making authority, and opportunities for skill

utilization and learning. It also emphasizes the significance of feedback and communication from managers and co-workers in fostering employee engagement.

Secondly, the hypothesis regarding the positive and significant influence of reward and recognition on employee engagement is also supported. This suggests that acknowledging and appreciating employees' contributions and achievements through praise, rewards, and tokens of appreciation can significantly impact their level of engagement. It underscores the role of positive reinforcement and acknowledgement in motivating and engaging employees.

However, it is worth noting that the hypothesis related to the working environment's influence on employee engagement was rejected. This indicates that the specific aspects of the working environment examined in the study did not show a significant relationship with employee engagement. Further exploration may be needed to understand the underlying factors contributing to this result.

Summary and Conclusion

The main purpose of this study is to investigate that factor affecting Employee Engagement in Commercial Bank of Ethiopia. To examine factor affecting Employee Engagement, the specific objectives were : examining the perceptions of employees towards Employee Engagement in the case bank; assessing the firm's employee engagement; analyzing the relationship between independent variables (job characteristic, reward and recognition, perceived organizational support, perceived supervisor support, working environment and internal locus of control) and dependent variable (employee engagement) and to identifying the relative influence of each independent variables on employee engagement of the case bank.

In addition, the result of correlation analysis was made. In this regard Table 4.11 shows that all the independent variables (job characteristic, reward and recognition, perceived organizational support, perceived supervisor support, working environment and internal locus of control) are positively and significantly correlated with the dependent variable (employee engagement) at 1% level of significance ($P < 0.000$). The highest correlation is attached to job characteristic ($r = 0.891$), followed by perceived supervisor support ($r = 0.856$), working environment ($r = 0.816$), Internal locus of Control ($r = 0.767$), reward and recognition ($r = 0.707$) and perceived organizational support ($r = 0.682$).

This study supports the presence of job characteristics, rewards and recognition, perceived organization support and perceived supervisor support, working environment and internal locus of control models of employee engagement. The results have important implications for assisting managers and companies to better understand and control factors that may lead to improved levels of employee engagement. In conclusion, the findings of the study provide valuable insights into the determinants of employee engagement in the commercial bank of Addis Ababa. The results highlight the significant influence of job characteristics, reward and recognition, perceived organizational support, and perceived supervisor support on employee engagement. These factors play a crucial role in creating a positive work environment and fostering a sense of motivation and commitment among employees.

Recommendation

Based on the above findings, one key recommendation for organizations in the commercial banking sector in Addis Ababa is to prioritize and invest in the factors that have been identified as significant determinants of employee engagement.

- ✓ Firstly, organizations should focus on improving job characteristics by providing employees with

meaningful and challenging tasks, opportunities for skill development, and a sense of autonomy in their work. This can be achieved through job redesign, clear goal setting, and regular feedback mechanisms. By enhancing job characteristics, organizations can increase employee engagement and satisfaction.

- ✓ Secondly, organizations should establish robust reward and recognition programs that acknowledge and appreciate employees' contributions. Recognizing and rewarding employees for their efforts and achievements can create a positive work environment and foster a sense of motivation and commitment.
- ✓ Thirdly, it is crucial for organizations to prioritize perceived organizational support and perceived supervisor support. This can be achieved through open communication channels, supportive leadership styles, and opportunities for employees to voice their opinions and concerns. Creating a culture of support and care can enhance employee engagement and well-being.
- ✓ Lastly, although the study did not find a significant relationship between the working environment and employee engagement, it is still important for organizations to ensure a comfortable and conducive physical work environment. Providing adequate facilities, resources, and a pleasant atmosphere can contribute to overall employee satisfaction and productivity. By implementing these recommendations, organizations can foster a positive work environment, enhance employee engagement, and ultimately drive organizational success in the commercial banking sector.

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